

D7.5

First report on dissemination

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1 Executive Summary

This Document reports about the dissemination actions put in place by the MaX CoE in the first 18 months of activity (from September 2015 to February 2017). MaX dissemination includes actions aimed at researchers and academia, as well as dedicated actions targeting industrial end-users. Scientific achievements have been published in internationally recognised, peer-reviewed scientific journals. The efforts towards researchers, graduate students and (potential) academic users has also taken advantage of typical Conference and Workshop channels. MaX members have given invited and contributed talks to conferences, workshops, and seminars, covering all range of subjects related to the CoE activity (from methodological developments to improvement of HPC performances and technology exploitation, to cutting edge computational studies of scientific test cases). The above activities represent the bulk of the dissemination actions of MaX.

Other dissemination activities are the organization of a large scale conference in the field of electronic structure (XVIII Total ENergy and Force Methods Conference, Trieste, IT), as well as a number of training events related to the flagship codes, also allowing for dissemination of recent methodological and software developments. In January 2017, a general MaX meeting was organized in Trieste, in connection with the Total Energy conference.

Dissemination actions specifically directed to industry --especially individual meetings and the industry-specific website-- are described in deliverable D5.3 on industrial outreach, which covers the same time period of the present document.

2 Participation to Conferences, Workshops, Seminars

MAX members have systematically and actively participated in the major domain specific (electronic structure and materials science) and high performance computing (HPC) conferences. Moreover, MaX researchers have been invited to give seminars and lectures in a number of different environments.

2.1 List of Invited talks, lectures, and seminars

A list of invited talks given by MaX members in international conferences about MaX topics is given in the following (List 1).

The high number of talks shows the commitment of scientists to disseminate MaX knowledge and results, in Europe and beyond. Subjects covered range from methodological and algorithmic developments, to scientific software implementation in HPC environment, to the actual exploitation of the MaX flagship codes (together with their new functionalities and performance improvements) in scientific case studies.

In Table 1 a (partial) list of contributed talks or posters is also given.

List 1. Invited talks, lectures, and seminars.

(The format given is *Title. Speaker. Event. Place. Date*)

(a) About Max

1. *Designing Materials with High Performance Computing.*
Guido Chiarotti (Cnr Nano). International Conference of Synthetic Population. Lucca (IT). 22/02/2017
2. *Materials design at the exascale. The MaX Center of Excellence.*
Elisa Molinari (Cnr Nano). Big Data Table of Regione Emilia Romagna, Bologna (IT). 03/02/2017
3. *Designing materials with High Performance Computing.*
Carlo Cavazzoni (Cineca). EoCoE project meeting. Rome (IT). 02/12/2016
4. *MaX Center of Excellence: Materials at the Exascale.*
Pablo Ordejón (ICN2). E-CAM Industry Meeting. Mainz (DE). 07/09/2016
5. *Women across science disciplines: a scientist's perspective, the MaX experience*
Elisa Molinari (Cnr Nano). European Regional Meeting of the Global Research Council 2016 Summit, Roma (IT) 05/11/2015
6. *The MaX Center of Excellence <http://www.eocoe.eu/>.*
Daniele Varsano (Cnr Nano). EoCoE Kick-off Meeting. Maison de la Simulation, Saclay (FR). 05/10/2015
7. *Materials design at the exascale. The MaX Center of Excellence.*
Elisa Molinari (Cnr Nano). Psi-k conference 2015, San Sebastian (ES). 09/09/2015
(about 800 participants, special plenary session on CoEs)

(b) About pilot codes

8. *The ADES ecosystem.*
Nicola Marzari (EPFL). UC Berkeley. Berkeley, CA (US). 3/02/2017
9. *Connection of the FLEUR code to a computational science platform.*
Jens Broeder (Jülich). Plasmaphysik (IEK-4) Seminar. Forschungszentrum Jülich (DE). 06/12/2016
10. *Ab-Initio Many-Body Perturbation-Theory: the Yambo code.*
Davide Sangalli (EPFL). Material Science codes on innovative HPC architectures: targeting exascale @ Cineca. Casalecchio di Reno (IT). 06/12/2016
11. *The FLEUR code.*
Daniel Wortmann (Jülich). Material Science codes on innovative HPC architectures: targeting exascale @ Cineca. Casalecchio di Reno (IT). 06/12/2016
12. *Materials modelling and discovery with QUANTUM ESPRESSO.*
Stefano Baroni (SISSA). First International Symposium on Research and Education in Computational Science. Tokyo (JP). 29-30/11/2016
13. *Adventures in Flatland.*

- Nicola Marzari (EPFL). PGI Colloquium. Jülich (DE). 18/11/2016
14. *Using AiiDA to accelerate discovery in Materials Science: the case of 2D materials.*
Davide Campi (EPFL). Jülich, MARVEL, MaX get together on AiiDA and its applications for Material design. Forschungszentrum Jülich (DE). 17/11/2016
 15. *Scaling out Quantum ESPRESSO on Marconi System.*
Carlo Cavazzoni (Cineca). Supercomputing 2016. Salt Lake City (US). 14/11/2016
 16. *ADES: automation, data, environment, and storage.*
Nicola Marzari (EPFL). EUDAT meeting. Bern (CH). 9/11/2016
 17. *Managing Computational Materials Science: The ADES model and the AiiDA infrastructure.*
Giovanni Pizzi (EPFL). International Conference on Electronic Materials and Nanotechnology for Green Environment (ENGE2016). Jeju (KR). 06/11/2016
 18. *Integrating Materials databases: the AiiDA experience.*
Giovanni Pizzi (EPFL). Lorentz Center workshop “Open Databases Integration for Materials Design”. Snellius, Leiden (BE). 24/10/2016
 19. *The Ades Model.*
Nicola Marzari (EPFL). CECAM Lorentz Optimal Materials Design Workshop. Leiden (NL). 23/10/2016
 20. *Quantum ESPRESSO code & the challenge of continuous software innovation for HPC.*
Carlo Cavazzoni (Cineca). Workshop on programming models for exascale. Manchester (UK). 12/10/2016
 21. *Managing computational materials science: The ADES model and the AiiDA infrastructure.*
Giovanni Pizzi (EPFL). College on Multiscale Computational Modeling of Materials for Energy Applications. Trieste (IT). 14/07/2016
 22. *Quantum ESPRESSO Open Source community code: the challenge of continuous software innovation for HPC.*
Carlo Cavazzoni (Cineca). PASC2016. Lausanne (CH). 08/06/2016
 23. *The ADES model for Computational Materials Science and its implementation in the AiiDA infrastructure.*
Giovanni Pizzi (EPFL). SeRC 7th annual meeting. Stockholm (SE). 01/06/2016
 24. *Design and Implementation of the PEXSI Solver Interface in SIESTA.*
Alberto Garcia. SIAM Conference on Parallel Processing for Scientific Computing (PP16). Paris (FR). 14/04/2016
 25. *The ADES model and the AiiDA infrastructure for Computational Materials Science.*
Giovanni Pizzi (EPFL). SOS20 conference on Supercomputing. Asheville, NC (US). 23/03/2016
 26. *The Yambo code: a comprehensive tool to perform ab-initio simulations of equilibrium and out-of-equilibrium properties.*
Andrea Marini (Cnr ISM). APS March Meeting. Baltimore, MD (US). 16/03/2016

27. *Metadata for a code-independent format: the experience with AiiDA.*
Giovanni Pizzi (EPFL). CECAM workshop: "Towards a Common Format for Computational Materials Science Data". Lausanne (CH). 26/01/2016
28. *Managing simulations: The ADES model and the AiiDA software platform.*
Giovanni Pizzi (EPFL). Master in HPC. ICTP, Trieste (IT). 15/12/2015
29. *The ADES Model.*
Nicola Marzari (EPFL). MRS Boston Symposium AAA. Boston, MA (US). 30/11/2015
30. *Storing and sharing computer simulations: the ADES model and AiiDA.*
Giovanni Pizzi (EPFL). CECAM workshop: "Big Data of Materials Science - Critical Next Steps". Lausanne (CH). 30/11/2015
31. *The ADES model and the AiiDA infrastructure for Computational Materials Science.*
Giovanni Pizzi (EPFL). Psi-K 2015 conference. San Sebastian (ES). 07/09/2015

(c) About computational science

32. *Car and Parrinello meet Green and Kubo: simulating atomic heat transport from equilibrium ab-initio molecular dynamics.*
Stefano Baroni (SISSA). Department of Materials at the University of Oxford. Oxford (UK). 24/02/2017
33. *Car and Parrinello meet Green and Kubo: simulating atomic heat transport from equilibrium ab-initio molecular dynamics.*
Stefano Baroni (SISSA). Department of Physics at the University of Cambridge. Cambridge (UK). 23/02/2017
34. *Adventures in Flatland.*
Nicola Marzari (EPFL). University of Basel. Basel (CH). 22/02/2017
35. *Car and Parrinello meet Green and Kubo: simulating atomic heat transport from equilibrium ab-initio molecular dynamics.*
Stefano Baroni (SISSA). Department of Earth Sciences at University College London. London (UK). 20/02/2017
36. *Marconi performance, comparison with BGQ and between KNL and BDW.*
Carlo Cavazzoni (Cineca). HPCXXL 2017 Winter Workshop. Cineca, Casalecchio di Reno (IT). 07/02/2017
37. *Modeling materials using quantum mechanics and digital computers: the plane-wave pseudo potential way.*
Stefano Baroni (SISSA). Advanced Workshop on High-Performance & High-Throughput Materials Simulations using QUANTUM ESPRESSO, the Abdus Salam International Centre for Theoretical Physics. Trieste (IT). 16-27/01/2017
38. *Car and Parrinello meet Green and Kubo: simulating atomic heat transport from equilibrium ab-initio molecular dynamics.*
Stefano Baroni (SISSA). 18th International Workshop on Computational Physics and Materials Science: Total Energy and Force Methods, the Abdus Salam International Centre for Theoretical Physics. Trieste (IT). 12-14/01/2017

39. *Exciton binding and instabilities in quasi-1D Carbon systems.*
Elisa Molinari (Cnr-NANO). 18th International Workshop on Computational Physics and Materials Science: Total Energy and Force Methods, the Abdus Salam International Centre for Theoretical Physics. Trieste (IT). 12-14/01/2017
40. *Car and Parrinello meet Green and Kubo: simulating atomic heat transport from equilibrium ab-initio molecular dynamics.*
Stefano Baroni (SISSA). Department of Physics, the University of Tokyo. Tokyo (JP). 28/11/2016
41. *Developing the third generation CALPHAD databases.*
Mauro Palumbo (SISSA). KTH, Stockholm (SE). 15/11/2016
42. *High-throughput materials discovery: methods, tools and results.*
Giovanni Pizzi (EPFL). Department seminar at Seoul National University. Seoul (KR). 09/11/2016
43. *Automatic topography of complex and multidimensional probability distributions.*
Alessandro Laio (SISSA). Cnr Nano S3 & Dept. FIM, University of Modena and Reggio Emilia. Modena (IT). 3/11/2016
44. *Ultra-fast processes in realistic materials: challenges and perspectives at the beginning of a new atomistic simulations.*
Andrea Marini (Cnr ISM). Colloquium at Physics and Materials Science Research Unit, University of Luxembourg. Luxembourg. 26/10/2016
45. *Orbital-DFT for spectroscopies.*
Andrea Ferretti (Cnr Nano). Conference: What about U? - Effects of Hubbard Interactions and Hund's Coupling in Solids. Trieste (IT). 20/10/2016
46. *Energies and Spectra from functional theories.*
Nicola Marzari (EPFL). Seminar at University of Chicago. Chicago (IL). 19/10/2016
47. *Adventures in Flatland.*
Nicola Marzari (EPFL). ChiMaD seminar. Evanston, IL (US). 18/10/2016
48. *Understanding the early stages of exciton formation and charge separation in organics.*
Elisa Molinari (Cnr Nano). Cecam Workshop on Charge carrier dynamics in nanostructures: optoelectronic and photo-stimulated processes. Bremen (DE). 11/10/2016
49. *Boltzmann in materials - tales of heat and electricity, the death of phonons, and the birth of relaxons.*
Nicola Marzari (EPFL). Second Chalmers symposium on Nanoscale Thermal Transport. Goteborg (SE). 7/10/2016
50. *Electron and Optical spectroscopies of Graphene nano ribbons.*
Andrea Ferretti (Cnr Nano). Brazil MRS. Campinas, Sao Paulo (BR). 29/09/2016
51. *Layered and 2D materials: electronic properties and structural instabilities from First Principles*
Pablo Ordejón (ICN2). 2016 International Graphene Innovation Conference. Qingdao

(CH). 23/09/2016

52. *Science 2.0: How computational materials science will change your world.*
Nicola Marzari (EPFL). Materials Today's New Scientist Live event. London (UK). 23/09/2016
53. *Electron and Optical spectroscopies of Graphene nanoribbons.*
Andrea Ferretti (Cnr Nano). NanoInnovation 2016. Rome (IT). 22/09/2016
54. *Bridging density functional and many body perturbation theory: orbital density dependence in electronic structure functionals.*
Andrea Ferretti (Cnr Nano). ECAM workshop "State of the Art in Electronic Structure". CECAM-UK-Hartree (UK). 14/09/2016
55. *Science 2.0: How computational materials science will change your world.*
Nicola Marzari (EPFL). ECAM workshop "State of the Art in Electronic Structure". Chester (UK). 14/09/2016
56. *Computational Exfoliation of All Known Inorganic Materials.*
Nicola Marzari (EPFL). Trends in Nanotechnology 2016. Fribourg (DE). 5/09/2016
57. *Exciting Nanosystems.*
Elisa Molinari (Cnr Nano). 26th Internat Conference of the Condensed Matter Division of the European Physical Society (CMD 26), Groeningen (NL). 05/09/2016
58. *Pump and Probe experiments described by first principles non--equilibrium Green's functions.*
Davide Sangalli (Cnr-ISM). CMD 26. Symposium 22: theoretical spectroscopy, Groeningen (NL). 05/09/2016
59. *Layered and 2D materials: electronic properties and structural instabilities from first principles.*
Pablo Ordejón. 30th Meeting of the European Crystallographic Association. Basel (CH). 31/08/2016
60. *Energies and spectra from functional theories.*
Nicola Marzari (EPFL). TACC 2016. Seattle, WA (US). 31/08/2016
61. *Orbital-dependent functionals: a personal history.*
Nicola Marzari (EPFL). The 2016 CAMD Summer School on Electronic Structure Theory and Materials Design. DTU Lyngby (DK). 18/08/2016
62. *Ultrafast electronic processes.*
Andrea Marini (Cnr ISM). CAMD summer school. Lyngby (DK). 14-19/08/2016
63. *An industrial age for materials' simulations.*
Nicola Marzari (EPFL). Inauguration, the VILLUM Centre for the Science of Sustainable Fuels and Chemicals. DTU Louisiana (DK). 11/08/2016
64. *Excited states without virtual orbitals.*
Stefano Baroni (SISSA). International Conference on Algorithms and Applications for Excited State Electronic Structure Theories, Beijing Computational Science Research Center. Beijing (CH), 8-10/08/2016.

65. *Post-DFT techniques.*
Andrea Marini (Cnr ISM). 1st NFFA-Europe Summer School. Barcelona (ES). 18/07/2016
66. *What am I doing here.*
Nicola Marzari (EPFL). Marvel junior retreat. Les Diablerets (CH). 18/07/2016
67. *Femto-second carrier dynamics and transient absorption in bulk Silicon.*
Davide Sangalli (Cnr ISM). Marseille condensed matter 2016: Optics and Magnetism. Marseille (FR). 12/07/2016
68. *Adventures in Flatland.*
Nicola Marzari (EPFL). City University of Hong Kong. Hong Kong (HK). 11/07/2016
69. *High-throughput prediction of novel 2d materials.*
Nicola Marzari (EPFL). ICEM Singapore. Singapore (SG) 07/07/2016
70. *Discovering novel materials and sharing materials data – Benefits and challenges.*
Giovanni Pizzi (EPFL). Open Data CH 2016 conference. Lausanne (CH). 14/06/2016
71. *Understanding the early stages of charge separation in organic photovoltaics.*
Elisa Molinari (Cnr Nano). Symposium in honour of Carlo Taliani, Bologna (I). 06/06/2016
72. *Too big or not too big? data and workflows in computational materials science.*
Nicola Marzari (EPFL). CECAM workshop. ETHZ, Lausanne (CH). 1/06/2016
73. *Where do we come from, what are we, where are we going.*
Nicola Marzari (EPFL). Plenary Speaker in honor of the Dean of Science at Aalto University. Helsinki (FI). 26/05/2016
74. *Boltzmann in materials - tales of heat and electricity, the death of phonons, and the birth of relaxons.*
Nicola Marzari (EPFL). Swiss Plasma Center Colloquium. Lausanne (CH). 20/05/2016
75. *Marrying Green-Kubo with density-functional theory.*
Stefano Baroni (SISSA). CPMD 2016 Conference, Institute for Molecular Engineering, University of Chicago. Chicago (IL). 18-20/05/2016
76. *Density Functional theory (2 lectures).*
Nicola Marzari (EPFL). Biennial school of ASESMA (asesma.org). Accra (GH). 13-16/05/2016
77. *Adventures in Flatland.*
Nicola Marzari (EPFL). International Max Planck Research School. Dresden (DE). 11/05/2016
78. *An industrial age for materials' simulations.*
Nicola Marzari (EPFL). Bochum (DE). 2/05/2016
79. *Many body interactions and optical excitations in graphene nanostructures.*
Elisa Molinari (Cnr Nano). 6th Graphene Conference, Graphene2016. Genova (IT). 20/04/2016

80. *2D or not 2D*
Nicola Marzari (EPFL). MRS Spring Meeting. Phoenix, AZ (US). 31/03/2016
81. *Electronic-structure simulations.*
Nicola Marzari (EPFL). EMMC workshop on metadata and interoperability. Brussels (BE). 10/03/2016
82. *The Agony and The Ecstasy.*
Nicola Marzari (EPFL). The Frontiers of Materials Modeling - TYC 10th Anniversary Symposium, London (UK). 17-19/2/2016
83. *Here and now: the intersection of computer science and computational science*
Nicola Marzari (EPFL). SISSA-ICTP Master in HPC workshop and ceremony. Trieste (IT). 10/02/2016
84. *A new approach to describe out-of-equilibrium processes in realistic materials based on the merging of Density-functional Theory with Many-Body Perturbation Theory.*
Andrea Marini (Cnr ISM). Christian-Albrechts-Universität. Kiel (DE). 2/02/2016
85. *Here and now: the intersection of computer science and computational science*
Nicola Marzari (EPFL). Human Brain Project, Geneva (CH). 20/01/2016
86. *Here and now: the intersection of computer science and computational science*
Nicola Marzari (EPFL). IC Colloquium, EPFL. Lausanne (CH). 7/12/2015
87. *PASC & co - Swiss efforts in materials.*
Nicola Marzari (EPFL). PASC Review, Lugano (CH). 3/12/2015
88. *Where Do We Come From What Are We Where Are We Going.*
Nicola Marzari (EPFL). Electronic Structure Theory for the Accelerated Design of Structural Materials ESTADSM 2015. Moscow (RU). 28/10/2015
89. *The density is not enough.*
Nicola Marzari (EPFL). ViCOM, Vienna (AT). 15/10/2015.
90. *L'aqua xe morta.*
Nicola Marzari (EPFL). Workshop on Electrochemistry, Université Pierre et Marie Curie, Paris (FR). 2/10/2015
91. *Where Do We Come From What Are We Where Are We Going.*
Nicola Marzari (EPFL). CECAM Strategy Meeting. Lausanne (CH). 16/09/2015
92. *A new approach to describe out-of-equilibrium processes in realistic materials based on the merging of Density-functional Theory with Many-Body Perturbation Theory.*
Andrea Marini (Cnr ISM). Psi-K conference. San Sebastian (ES). 10/09/2015
93. *What I cannot compute I do not understand: fathoming heat transport from the struggle to simulate it.*
Stefano Baroni (SISSA). 19th Symposium on Condensed Matter Physics. Belgrade (RS). 7-11/09/2015

Table 1. List of (selected) contributed talks and posters

Date	Name of Event	Place	Title of presentation
26/01/2017	Advanced Workshop on High-Performance & High-Throughput Materials Simulations using Quantum ESPRESSO	ICTP, Trieste (IT)	Advanced Molecular Dynamics. Thermostats, Barostats and Nuclear Quantum Effects
26/01/2017	Advanced Workshop on High-Performance & High-Throughput Materials Simulations using Quantum ESPRESSO	ICTP, Trieste (IT)	Hands-on: Advanced Molecular Dynamics using i-PI and QE
03/10/2016	CompoBioMed Kick-off	London (UK)	Designing Materials with HPC
28/09/2016	Brazil MRS 2016	Campinas, Sao Paulo (BR)	Materials design at the exascale
23/06/2016	PRACE workshop on ISC16 High Performance	Frankfurt (DE)	HPC training in data and compute intensive research environment, constrains and affordances
13/06/2016	Path Integral Quantum Mechanics: Theory, Simulation and Application	CECAM – EPFL (CH)	Accelerating Path Integral Calculations
08/06/2016	Platform for advanced scientific computing conference PASC16	Lausanne (CH)	Domain Specific Libraries for Material Science Applications
07/03/2016	80. Jahrestagung der DPG und DPG-Frühjahrstagung	Regensburg (DE)	Density Functional Theory Simulations on Tungsten and Beryllium Alloys for ITER
05/10/2015	EoCoE Kick-off Meeting	Maison de la Simulation, Saclay (FR)	The MaX Center of Excellence
05/06/2016	IAS Symposium 2016	Forschungszentrum Jülich (DE)	The AiiDA plug-in for the FLEUR code and its first application on fusion relevant materials
12/04/2017	Ultra-fast phenomena in quantum physics: a challenge for theory & experiment	Lausanne (CH)	Pump and Probe experiments from first principles in bulk silicon
23/03/2017	Optical Nanospectroscopy III	Rome (IT)	Pump and Probe experiments from firstprinciples in bulk silicon
23/01/2017	HiPEAC 2017	Stockholm (SE)	MaX-Material Design at the Exascale, an European Centre of Excellence
13/01/2017	18th International Workshop on Computational Physics and Materials Science: Total Energy and Force Methods	ICTP, Trieste (IT)	
13/01/2017	18th International Workshop on Computational Physics and Materials Science: Total Energy and Force Methods	ICTP, Trieste (IT)	Multiple electrode (Ne≥1) support in the DFT+NEGF codeTransSIESTA
12/01/2017	18th International Workshop on Computational Physics and Materials Science: Total Energy and Force Methods	ICTP, Trieste (IT)	Computational design of novel 2d-materials for electronic applications

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12/01/2017	18th International Workshop on Computational Physics and Materials Science: Total Energy and Force Methods	ICTP, Trieste (IT)	Thermal conductivity of 2D materials from first principles
12/01/2017	18th International Workshop on Computational Physics and Materials Science: Total Energy and Force Methods	ICTP, Trieste (IT)	Thermal properties of graphene nanoflakes dispersed in DMF: a classical MD study including QM correction
2206/2016	MARVEL/Max/Psi-k Tutorial on high-throughput computations: general methods and applications using AiiDA	Lausanne, Switzerland	The AiiDA plug-in for the FLEUR code and its first application on fusion relevant materials
08/06/2016	Platform for advanced scientific computing conference PASC16	Lausanne, Switzerland	Scalable implementation of the FFT kernel for the plane-wave codes

2.2 List of Publications

A list of publications authored by MaX members is given below. These publications can be grouped in different categories, covering methodological, algorithmic, and technological developments connected to the MaX activities, as well as cutting edge applications of the MaX flagship codes to scientific cases of interest in the domain of materials science. We point out the number and high impact of several publications, as apparent from the Journal Impact Factors (IFs) (citations are often irrelevant because the publications are too recent).

All publications acknowledge MaX support (e.g., “We acknowledge support from the EU Centre of Excellence ‘MaX - Materials Design at the Exascale’ (Grant No. 676598)” or alike).

Publications flagged with OA already satisfy Open Access rules. We are currently working with partners to fulfill such requirements also for the other publications.

1. Anomalous Temperature Dependence of the Band Gap in Black Phosphorus.
C. E. P. Villegas, A. R. Rocha, A. Marini. Nano Letters 16, 5095-5101 (2016). Doi: [10.1021/acs.nanolett.6b02035](https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.nanolett.6b02035)
Impact (Web of Science). Journal IF 2015: 13,779 - Citations: 3 - Usage count since 2013: 49
2. Photo-Induced Bandgap Renormalization Governs the Ultrafast Response of Single-Layer MoS₂.
E. E. A. Pogna, M. Marsili, D. De Fazio, S. Dal Conte, C. Manzoni, D. Sangalli, D. Yoon, A. Lombardo, A. C. Ferrari, A. Marini, G. Cerullo, D. Prezzi. ACS NANO 10, 1182-1188 (2016). Doi: [10.1021/acs.nano.5b06488](https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.nano.5b06488)
Impact (Web of Science). Journal IF 2015: 13,334 - Citations: 17 - Usage count since 2013: 101
3. Electron-vibration coupling induced renormalization in the photoemission spectrum of diamondoids.
A. Gali, T. Demjan, M. Voros, G. Thiering, E. Cannuccia, A. Marini. Nature Comm. 7, 11327 (2016). Doi: [10.1038/ncomms11327](https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms11327) [OA]
Impact (Web of Science). Journal IF 2015: 11,329 - Citations: 0 - Usage count since 2013: 17
4. First-principles photoemission spectroscopy in DNA and RNA nucleobases from Koopmans-compliant functionals.
N.L. Nguyen, G. Borghi, A. Ferretti, N. Marzari. J. Chem. Theory Comput. 8, 3948-3958 (2016). Doi: [10.1021/acs.jctc.6b00145](https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jctc.6b00145)
Impact (Web of Science). Journal IF 2015: 5,301 - Citations: 0 - Usage count since 2013: 8
5. Multimodel Approach to the Optical Properties of Molecular Dyes in Solution.
I. Timrov, M. Micciarelli, M. Rosa, A. Calzolari, S. Baroni
J. Chem. Theory Comput. 12, 4423-4429 (2016). Doi: [10.1021/acs.jctc.6b00417](https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jctc.6b00417)
Impact (Web of Science). Journal IF 2015: 5,301 - Citations: 0 - Usage count since 2013: 2
6. Sampling Molecular Conformers in Solution with Quantum Mechanical Accuracy at a

Nearly Molecular-Mechanics.

M. Rosa, M. Micciarelli, A. Laio, S. Baroni. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* 12, 4385-4389 (2016). Doi: [10.1021/acs.jctc.6b00470](https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jctc.6b00470)

Impact (Web of Science). Journal IF 2015: 5,301 - Citations: 0 - Usage count since 2013: 8

7. Electronic Structure Evolution during the Growth of Graphene Nanoribbons on Au(110).
A Della Pia, G. Avvisati, O. Ourdjini, C. Cardoso, D. Varsano, D. Prezzi, A. Ferretti, C. Mariani, M.G. Betti. *J. Chem. Phys. C* 120, 7323-7331 (2016). Doi: [10.1021/acs.jpcc.5b11884](https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcc.5b11884)

Impact (Web of Science). Journal IF 2015: 4,509 - Citations: 0 - Usage count since 2013: 30

8. Anomalous scaling and breakdown of conventional density functional theory methods for the description of Mott phenomena and stretched bonds.
ZJ Ying, V. Brosco, GM. Lopez, D. Varsano, P. Gori-Giorgi, J. Lorenzana. *Phys. Rev. B* 94, 75154 (2016). Doi: [10.1103/PhysRevB.94.075154](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.94.075154)

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3 MaX meeting, Trieste (IT), January 10-11, 2017

On January 10-11, 2017 in Trieste (IT) the MaX meeting took place, attended by about 45 people. The meeting was held on teleconference to allow for remote participation. The main focus was an overview of the activities on-going within the centre, to discuss them, and to lay the foundation for future activities and interactions, both within and outside the centre.

The meeting was organised in several sessions, all based on contributions from invited speakers (from within and outside the network) followed by time for open discussion. In the first part, a lively discussion on talks and brainstorming on scientific and technological perspectives took place, debating topics such as the future of HPC, data analytics in materials science, multiscale approaches, time-resolved and emerging spectroscopies, the convergence of high-throughput and high-performance computing, advanced sampling and dynamics. These subjects were considered key aspects in order to drive and design a future strategy for the Centre.

A great contribution to the debate on future perspectives and possible synergies between Quantum Technologies and HPC initiatives was given by Dr. Norbert Schuch, Leader of the "Entanglement of Complex Quantum Systems" research group of the Max-Planck-Institute of Quantum Optics (<http://www.mpq.mpg.de/~nys>). Dr. Schuch gave a highly-appreciated talk about "Quantum Information and Technology and possible overlaps with high-performance electronic structure calculations", which set the tone for a vivid discussion.

Afterwards, a number of presentations reporting on MaX activities, status of on-going tasks and deliverables took place. All WP leaders, backed by several participants to WPs, told the assembly about the status of their WP and their contributions to the project as a whole. The overall agreement was that the centre is on track, targeting all its objectives, including the development of materials science applications able to exploit present and future HPC architecture (towards the exascale), and the provisioning of services to the community, by means of the dedicated unique user entry point. Code scalability, performance, and functionality were greatly enhanced by the MaX action and also further complemented by high-level workflows and turn-key solutions through the AiiDA framework for materials informatics. The integration of the codes within this framework, already at a very advanced stage, represents a crucial asset for the Quantum-as-a-Service business model (QaaS, an easy to deploy and easy to execute VM based service) which also was discussed at depth within the meeting. The meeting showed the collaborative and integrated spirit of MaX, in which scientific excellence is combined with the ability to execute and a pragmatic view focussed on the implementation of the CoE's tasks.

MaX coordinator prof. Molinari led then an overall discussion about MaX future and strategies, followed by a meeting of the General Assembly, held during the final session of the event. The whole program of the meeting is reported below.

Trieste MaX Meeting – Tentative Program
(All sessions take place at SISSA, Via Bonomea 265)

MONDAY, JANUARY 9, 2017	
18.00-20.00	Welcome and Get Together (Hotel Savoy)
TUESDAY, JANUARY 10, 2017	
09:00-09:15	Welcome (S. Ruffo , Director, SISSA) Opening: agenda & goals of the meeting (E. Molinari)
	SESSION 1 (talks & brain storming on scientific/technological perspectives)
09:15-09:50	T. Schülthess : The future of HPC: a perspective (25' +10' discussion)
09:50-10:25	A. Laio : Analytics in material science: a perspective (25' +10' discussion)
10:25-11:10	S. Baroni : Multiscale approaches: a perspective (25' +10' + 10' discussion) includes comments by C. Cavazzoni on tech aspects of QE - Lammps integration
11:10-11:40	<i>coffee break</i>
	SESSION 2 (talks & brain storming on scientific/technological perspectives, cont.d)
11:40-12:15	A. Marini : Time Resolved Spectroscopies: a perspective (25' +10' discussion)
12:15-13:00	Panel discussion : sci-tech aspects of HPC-HTC convergence, coordinated by E. Laure and N. Marzari (10'+10' intro + 25' discussion, including comments by HPC centers on perspectives of HPC/data federation)
13:00-14:00	<i>Lunch</i>
14:00-14:35	M. Ceriotti : Advanced sampling and dynamics: a perspective (25' +10' discussion)
	SESSION 3 (reports on MaX activities)
14:35-16:05	WP1 activity report, status of ongoing tasks and deliverables S. Baroni : Overview 15' each flagship code: 5*12' discussion 15'
16:05-16:30	<i>coffee break</i>
	SESSION 4 (reports on MaX activities, cont.d)
16:30-17:45	WP4 activity report, status of ongoing tasks and deliverables C. Cavazzoni : Overview 15' specific activities 3*15' discussion 15'
17:45-18:15	WP6 activity report, status of ongoing tasks and deliverables D. Varsano : Overview 15' discussion 15'
	SESSION 5 (talk & brain storming on scientific/technological perspectives, cont.d)
18:15-19:15	15:15
20:15	<i>social dinner (Hotel Savoy)</i>

WEDNESDAY, JANUARY 11, 2017	
	SESSION 6 (reports on MaX activities, cont.d)
08:30-09:30	WP3 activity report, status of ongoing tasks and deliverables N. Marzari: Overview 15' specific activities 3*15'
09:30-10:00	WP2 activity report, status of ongoing tasks and deliverables P. Ordejón: Overview: observatory and pilots update
10:00-11:00	WP5 activity report, status of ongoing tasks and deliverables C. Daffara: industry G. Chiarotti: services
11:00-11:20	<i>Coffee break</i>
	SESSION 7 (brain storming on perspectives)
11:20-12:30	Discussion: future of MaX and CoEs (short intro: E. Molinari)
12:30-13:20	<i>Lunch</i>
	SESSION 8 (reports on MaX activities, cont.d)
13:20-13:45	WP7 activity report, status of ongoing tasks and deliverables
PARALLEL SESSIONS	
13:45-15:15	Separate working groups & WP activities (schedule to be decided during the first day of the meeting)
	General Assembly (PI's + delegates/invited participants)
15:15-17:30	among the working groups: - QaaS (Quantum as a Service) working group
	<i>Coffee available all along</i>
17:30	End of the meeting

Types of sessions

type A - vision and brainstorming on sci & technol perspectives
type B - reporting on MaX activities
type C - discussions and decisions on MaX and perspectives (including General Assembly)

Get together & dinner venue:

Hotel Savoy Restaurant

Riva del Mandracchio n. 4

34124 Trieste

Tel. +39.040 7794 730 | 040 7794 1

Fax. +39.040 6382 60

<http://www.savoytrieste.it>

Opening of the meeting, prof. Elisa Molinari PI

The Meeting was organized by Cnr with the strong support and collaboration of Sissa.

As far as communication is concerned, a dedicated webpage in the MaX website was prepared in order to convey all necessary information to attendants (<http://www.max-centre.eu/max-meeting-trieste/>) and at the end of the meeting all presentations were collected and put to partners' disposal in a folder in the MaX intranet.

Sissa's press office prepared with the Cnr node a press release (https://www.sissa.it/sites/default/files/images/documents/communication_area/comunicati_stampa/Supercomputers%20for%20super%20materials.pdf) about the event. The meeting was covered by a live tweeting on Max's Twitter account @max_center2 and on other accounts (e.g., Cnr Press Office @StampaCnr, Sissa @Sissaschool, Cineca @Cineca1969).

Images from the meeting

4 Dissemination towards industry

Dissemination towards industry is described in deliverable D5.3 “Report on the industrial outreach activities and CoE services”, in particular see the section 5 “Data on the Industrial website”.

5 Dissemination via Training

MaX dissemination has been also positively impacted by a number of training/tutorial events organized by MaX members as part of WP6 activities. In fact, recent methodological and algorithmic developments related to the MaX flagship codes have been presented, technically described, and taught during these events, providing actual opportunities for disseminating latest scientific developments. The list of MaX training events is reported in Deliverable D6.3 and we refer the reader to that document for further details.

6 Conclusions and outlook

MaX dissemination strategy includes actions dedicated to researchers as well as actions targeting industrial end-users and HPC specialists. In our view, this dissemination blend is coherent with MaX objectives and allows a very effective integration of the MaX communities stakeholders. We emphasize the broad and high-profile international impact of all the dissemination actions.

We intend to continue along these dissemination lines and keywords, which will now be strengthened by showing success cases from the first months of MaX activities. Our major dissemination event, the final MaX conference (programmed for the end of the present year), will see the copresence of all the MaX communities. Besides dissemination to peers, we plan increased dissemination to a broader audience.

Finally, the MaX newsletter ([link](#)), whose first number was distributed while writing the present document, will offer a new regular channel for MaX dissemination and communication philosophy. We will be able to report about it in detail in forthcoming deliverables.

